

Dissociative Equilibrium in Aqueous Solution of MgSO_4 from 278.15 to 308.15 K

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The pK_s of MgSO_4 in aqueous solution determined from the e.m.f. values of cell

at 278.15, 288.15, 298.15 and 308.15 K are 3.037, 2.958, 2.877 and 2.803, respectively while the ΔG° 's at these temperatures are 16.17, 16.32, 16.42 and 16.54 kJ mol^{-1} . ΔS° and ΔH° values over the temperature range are constant and are $-11.8 \text{ J mol}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ and 12.9 kJ mol^{-1} .

THE dissociation constant of MgSO_4 at 291.15 K was determined by Davies¹ ($6.1 \times 10^{-8} \text{ mol kg}^{-1}$) and Dunsmore and James² ($6.2 \times 10^{-8} \text{ mol kg}^{-1}$) by conductometric method. Since sulphates of bivalent metals are hydrolysed in aqueous solutions, these values may be slightly higher than the correct values. So Jones and Monk³ and later Nair and Nancollas⁴ determined the dissociation constants of MgSO_4 from 273.15 to 308.15 K from the e.m.f. values of cell (C-1).

The pK values obtained by the two sets of authors at a number of temperatures differed from one another and were unsatisfactory in other respects too⁵. Recently, Emara and Lin⁶ determined the dissociation constant of MgSO_4 from spectrophotometric and e.m.f. data at 298.15 K only using Davies equation and obtained a value 4.587×10^{-8} .

Hence we have redetermined the values of pK of MgSO_4 in aqueous solution from 278.15 to 308.15 K in steps of 10 K, utilising the e.m.f. data obtained with cell (C-2). The thermodynamic quantities relating to the dissociation of MgSO_4 have been determined from these pK values.

Experimental

Cell (C-2) was set up keeping $c_2/c_1=5$ and the minimum concentration of H_2SO_4 used was $8 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol lit}^{-1}$, since at concentrations lower than this Hg_2SO_4 might have hydrolysed⁷. Experimental solutions used had ionic strength of less than 0.05 mol lit^{-1} . Double distilled water was used for the

preparation of solutions. Standard solution of H_2SO_4 , prepared from E. Merck, G.R. sample was

standardised against borax. Magnesium content of the stock solution of MgSO_4 prepared from E. Merck, G.R. sample in dilute H_2SO_4 was estimated volumetrically against standard EDTA and the sulphate in the solution was estimated gravimetrically as BaSO_4 . All experimental solutions were prepared by appropriately diluting the stock solution strictly at the experimental temperatures concerned and were deoxygenated by presaturated N_2 gas. The electrode vessels, bridge and the setting up of cell⁹ and the thermostat and the potentiometer assembly¹⁰ were the same as described earlier. Duplicate cells were used, the e.m.f. of which agreed with each other within 0.1 mV. The recorded e.m.f. values in absolute volt are the mean of the two e.m.f. values and are shown in Tables 1 to 4.

Results and Discussion

The e.m.f. of cell (C-2) is given by equation (1).

$$E = E^\circ - \frac{2.3026 RT}{2 F} \log [\text{H}]^2 [\text{SO}_4] - \frac{2.3026 RT}{2 F} \log f_{\text{H}}^2 f_{\text{SO}_4} \dots (1)$$

It was found in this laboratory that equation (2) fairly correctly represents the activity coefficient f_i of an ion in a solution.

$$-\log f_i = Az_1^2 \sqrt{\mu} - b_1 \mu \dots (2)$$

In equation (2), A is Debye-Hückel constant in $\text{mol}^{-\frac{1}{2}} \text{lit}^{\frac{1}{2}}$ and b_1 is an empirical constant which is additive in nature and is reasonably independent of the composition of the ionic atmosphere, provided its composition is not drastically changed. Applying equation (2) in (1) and putting $k = \frac{2.3026 RT}{F}$, we have

$$E = E^\circ - \frac{k}{2} \log [\text{H}]^2 [\text{SO}_4] + 3kA \sqrt{\mu} - b_1 \mu \dots (3)$$

where $b = (2b_{\text{H}} + b_{\text{SO}_4})$.

TABLE 4—STOICHIOMETRIC MOLARITIES AND MOLARITIES OF VARIOUS IONIC SPECIES IN CELL (C-2) AT 308.15K

[MgSO ₄] × 10 ³	[H ₂ SO ₄] × 10 ³	E Abs. volt	[H ⁺] × 10 ³	[SO ₄ ²⁻] × 10 ³	[Hg ₂ ²⁺] × 10 ³	[Mg ²⁺] × 10 ³	μ × 10 ³	K _c × 10 ³	log K _c - 8A√μ	f _{Mg} f _{SO₄}
4.005	0.807	0.17324	1.254	3.826	0.587	2.791	14.218	0.8794	3.4920	0.1864
5.011	1.010	0.16658	1.510	4.670	0.518	3.652	18.690	1.2548	3.5309	0.1930
6.002	1.209	0.16125	1.749	5.470	0.470	4.461	22.012	1.5881	3.5895	0.1049
7.002	1.411	0.15688	1.976	6.274	0.432	5.277	25.378	1.9191	3.6218	0.0831
7.999	1.612	0.15305	2.181	7.192	0.397	6.226	29.242	2.5241	3.6921	0.0642
9.006	1.814	0.14976	2.376	8.125	0.368	7.195	33.190	3.2289	3.7526	0.0497
9.999	2.014	0.14691	2.550	9.124	0.343	8.245	37.438	4.2909	3.8292	0.0379

In the above tables the concentrations and the ionic strengths are in mol lit⁻¹.

TABLE 5—THERMODYNAMIC QUANTITIES FOR THE REACTION MgSO₄ ⇌ Mg²⁺ + SO₄²⁻

Temp. K	pK		ΔG°/kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH°/kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS°/J mol K ⁻¹
	Graphical	Statistical			
278.15	3.037	3.04 ± 0.076	16.2 ± 0.41	12.9 ± 0.23	-11.8 ± 0.5
288.15	2.958	2.958 ± 0.007	16.32 ± 0.04	12.9 ± 0.23	-11.8 ± 0.2
298.15	2.877	2.88 ± 0.027	16.4 ± 0.15	12.9 ± 0.23	-11.8 ± 0.3
308.15	2.800	2.80 ± 0.024	16.5 ± 0.14	12.9 ± 0.23	-11.8 ± 0.3

micromol lit⁻¹. These values have been recorded in Tables 1 to 4.

$$\text{Putting } K = \frac{a_{Mg} \times a_{SO_4}}{a_{MgSO_4}} \text{ and } K_c = \frac{[Mg][SO_4]}{[MgSO_4]}$$

$$\text{we get, } \log K_c - 8A\sqrt{\mu} = \log K - B\mu \quad \dots (14)$$

Plots of L.H.S. of equation (14) against μ at all the temperatures were found to be linear, the intercepts at μ=0 giving log K and the slopes B.

The plot of log K against $\frac{1}{T}$ is found to be linear

indicating the constancy of ΔH° over the temperature range. The value of ΔH° has been found from the slope of the line. ΔG° was found from equation (15) and ΔS° from equation (16).

$$\Delta G^\circ = 2.3026 RT \log K \quad \dots \dots (15)$$

$$T\Delta S^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - \Delta G^\circ \quad \dots \dots (16)$$

These values have been recorded in Table 5.

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References

1. C. W. DAVIES, *Trans. Farad. Soc.*, 1927, 23, 351.
2. H. S. DUNSMORE and J. C. JAMES, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 2925.
3. H. W. JONES and C. B. MONK, *Trans. Farad. Soc.*, 1952, 48, 929.
4. V. S. K. NAIR and G. H. NANCOLLAS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 3706.
5. S. N. PRASAD, Thesis, Patna University, 1981.
6. M. M. EMARA and C. T. LIN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 876.
7. M. H. LITZKY and R. W. STRONGTON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 5226.
8. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 8rd Edn., 1962, p. 298, 434, 462.
9. L. SHARMA and B. PRASAD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 47, 379.
10. A. K. GHOSH, J. C. GHOSH and B. PRASAD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 1194.
11. L. SHARMA and B. PRASAD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 46, 241.
12. L. SHARMA and B. PRASAD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 47, 193.